

ISic0798

I.Sicily inscription 0798

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

granite

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Sicilia

Place of origin (modern)

Sicily

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

ligature in the text (the editor does not give precise indications)

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. □ Θ(εοῖς) Κ(αταχθονίοις) □
2. Ἐπαφρό[δ]ελτος χρη
3. στὸς ἔζησεν ἔτη · μ ·
4. μῆν(ας) · ε · ἡμέρ(ας) · γ · σύνβι
5. ος ἰδίῳ ἀνδρὶ μνήμης χάρ
6. □ιν ἐποίησεν □

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644900

EDR 140905

EDCS 41300114

PHI 175758

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1975.0458

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 153

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